

New Line of Bioinks for 3D Bioprinting

CD Bioparticles, a leading manufacturer and supplier of numerous drug delivery products and services, announced the launch of its new line of [bioinks](#) for 3D bioprinting. The new bioinks are designed to be biocompatible and versatile, making them ideal for a wide range of applications, including 3D biological model construction and cultivation, tissue engineering, and drug delivery.

CD Bioparticles is dedicated to providing customers with standard and custom bioactive matrices in various material forms and compositions that can help customers overcome challenges, such as limited selection of crosslinkable biomaterials, low consistency of the gelation process leading to uncontrolled mechanical properties and crosslink density, and poor control of the purity of the biomaterial source. To better support researchers in the bioprinting industry, CD BioParticles now introduces a series of new bioinks based on a variety of natural and synthetic materials including GelMA, Alginate and HAMA.

For example, the [GelMA](#) is a photosensitive hydrogel bioink made from methacrylated gelatin (Gel-MA). It is biocompatible (cell viability > 90%), convenient to use and has a long structure retention time (more than 30 days). This white lyophilized powder retains the temperature-sensitive properties of gelatin and can be mixed with photoinitiators (e.g., LAP, 12959) to work under blue or ultraviolet light. It is compatible with most human and animal cells, and can be easily printed by mixing with cell suspensions. In addition, GelMA has a variety of packaging forms (gel, freeze-dried powder) to ensure its high performance.

Another example is the high-purity HAMA, which is synthesized by the reaction of hyaluronic acid. The main component of this product is HAMA (methacrylated hyaluronic acid, molecular weight 150k-250kDa), which has good biocompatibility and can be stimulated by UV light or visible light (blue light) and mixed with basic biomaterials or other bio-inks of Shangpu to form a three-dimensional structure with a certain intensity suitable for the growth and differentiation of cells.

HAMA can be applied to most human and animal cells and is particularly useful for constructing and culturing 3D biological models of joints, cartilage, skin, and cornea. It is easy to operate (e.g., fast dissolution, fast cross-linking, fast cross-linking and molding in only 10s) and can be customized to meet the specific needs of customers.

CD Bioparticles offers a wide range of unique biomaterial formulations and high quality biomaterials, optimized formulations and protocols for customer choice. These active biomatrices with controlled mechanical modulus can be used for various cell culture and tissue regeneration applications. Meanwhile, the company has strict standards for raw material screening and quality control to ensure the consistency of biomaterial composition and the accuracy of research results.

For more information, please visit <https://www.cd-bioparticles.net/bioinks>.

About CD Bioparticles

CD Bioparticles is an established drug delivery company that provides customized solutions for developing and manufacturing novel biocompatible drug delivery systems. It specializes in various formulation and drug delivery technologies, from conventional liposomes and PEGylated liposomes to polymer microspheres and nanoparticles for drug delivery. The company also provides contract research services for drug delivery formulation, formulation feasibility study, process development and scale-up, as well as analytical and non-clinical research services.